

MORPHOLOGY AND FRACTURE OF DISORDERED COMPOSITE MICROSTRUCTURES

Ryszard Pyrz

Institute of Mechanical Engineering
Aalborg University, 9220 Aalborg, Denmark

ABSTRACT

Variability in the arrangement of microstructural features and their cooperative interaction determine the physical characteristics of the material. A microfailure threshold is dominated by extreme fluctuations of the stress field, and these hotspots are strongly influenced by distribution pattern of inclusions. This is illustrated with four distinct distributions of fibres observed on transverse sections of unidirectional composites. Microcracking and fracture are simulated with a discrete model that maps the microstructure of transversely loaded fibre reinforced material onto irregular network of structural bonds. The bond properties are related to stress field that exists in the material during loading. Loading diagrams and percolating cracks are calculated for several simulated patterns and selected real microstructures.

INTRODUCTION

Microstructural features and their cooperative interaction determine physical characteristics of a material. This is particularly true for the description of strongly non-linear phenomena such as fracture. Neglecting geometrical disorder of fillers does not introduce a significant error in the prediction of elastic and transport properties. By contrast, fracture is a highly localized phenomenon, and the local geometrical disorder cannot be neglected. Continuum material models cannot capture the effect of random local material inhomogeneities on the localization of damage and failure. Recently appeared are models that use regular network of bonds with distributed strength to simulate fracture behaviour [1], [2]. What none of these models represent realistically is the geometrical disorder of bonds that should reflect positions of inclusions as they are placed in a real material. The present study employs the geometrical disorder by mapping the microstructure of transversely loaded unidirectional composite onto irregular network of bonds with properties related to the stress field that exists in the material under loading. The results reported testify to the great importance of this geometrical disorder in the mechanical behaviour of composites loaded so that they suffer microcracking and fracture.

ANALYSIS OF DISORDER

Several attempts have been made to determine parameters that characterize the distribution of fillers [3], [4], [5]. In [6], [7] the second-order statistics has been introduced to describe the distribution pattern of fibres. The second-order intensity function $K(r)$ for four patterns shown

in Fig. 1 is illustrated in Fig. 2. The function $K(r)$ is defined as the number of further fibres expected

Figure 1. Distribution of fibres: 1. cluster, 2. regular, 3. circular hard-core, 4. elliptical hard-core.

Figure 2. Second order intensity function $K(r)$.

to lie within a radial distance r of an arbitrary fibre and divided by the number of fibres per unit area of observation. The practical way of calculating $K(r)$ is presented in [6]. The function $K(r)$ discriminates different distribution of fibres indicating clustering or regularity in the pattern. A completely random pattern of points is related to the Poisson distribution which $K(r)$ is equal to πr^2 . For aggregated distributions, the $K(r)$ function lies above the line corresponding to the

Poisson set. The regular distribution exhibits a characteristic "stair" shape form of the $K(r)$ function indicating deterministic inter-point distances and horizontal fragments representing empty spaces at corresponding distances. The $K(r)$ function for hard-core models with certain degree of regularity is always placed below the Poisson $K(r)$ function. The circular hard-core distribution has been obtained by the imposition of the circular area for each generated fibre that is not accessible for any further generated point. For the ellipse hard-core distribution a prohibited area has an elliptic shape and all major axes are oriented horizontally. Diameters of the circles and major axes of the ellipses are equal, whereas minor axes of the ellipses are smaller by 30%. The $K(r)$ function detects a subtle regularity of the ellipse hard-core model as compared with the circle hard-core counterpart although both patterns are seemingly similar.

The characterization of more complex aspects of disorder may be facilitated by the introduction of mark correlations. In addition to position of fibres we introduce a further variable to be the "mark" of the fibre with a given position. The mark represents typical feature expressible by numbers which may correspond to the size and type of fibres or any field quantity known at the fibre spot [7]. In the present case maximal radial stresses of fibres interphases are taken as marks. The stresses have been calculated according to the procedure that takes into account interactions between neighbouring fibres [8], [9]. The mark correlation function corresponds to the conditional mean value of the marks product of a pair of fibres positioned distance r apart [7]. The mark correlation function equal to unity indicates lack of correlation between the marks and the positions of fibres. Figure 3 shows the mark correlation function for selected patterns. As expected there is no correlation for the regular pattern of fibres as maximal radial stresses are the same for all fibres. For other patterns the mark correlation function fluctuates tending to a value near unity at distance $r = r_0$, indicating that no further correlation exist at distance $r > r_0$ apart. Thus for distances $r > r_0$, the separation distance between fibres ceases to have an influence on stress values, and therefore the distance r_0 scales the local correlations between physical behaviour and geometrical arrangement of the microstructure. The

Figure 3. Mark correlation function.

calculation of stresses has been performed with fibres of $12 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter. The size of the measuring cell has been $512 \mu\text{m}$. The interaction distance for the clustered pattern $r_0 \approx 126 \mu\text{m}$ is larger than for hard-core models due to aggregation and consequently stronger interactions. Obviously, the most pronounced interactions exist for shortest inter-fibre distances. It is necessary to underline that the mark correlation depends upon the loading conditions. Figure 3 illustrates the case of mark correlation for the circular hard-core model loaded both uniaxially and biaxially. The correlation distance for a biaxial loading is larger than for an uniaxial case since the intensity of the stress field is increased by the imposition of the biaxial load.

THE BREAKING CHARACTERISTICS

The discrete model of fracture has been created as follows [10], [11]. The Dirichlet network of polygons is drawn on the transverse section of unidirectionally reinforced material with the centres of fibres as generating points. In this manner it is possible to identify all neighbours of a given fibre and to define uniquely the zone of influence for each pair of neighbouring fibres. Thus a total area of observation is divided into a set of contiguous quadrangles which embrace the pairwise zones of influence, Fig. 4. The investigated patterns of fibres placed within the

Figure 4. Discretized model.

window of observation is equipped with periodic boundary conditions and subjected to remote unit load in vertical direction. The stress components are calculated at the centres of gravity of four quadrangles into which the pairwise zone of influence is divided. Assuming an equivalence between the energy stored in the matrix material bounded by the pairwise zone of influence and the energy that would have existed if the zone of influence had been replaced by an elastic rod connecting centres of neighbouring fibres, the stiffness of rods may be calculated, and then the microstructure is transformed into a truss-like structure. The network is loaded vertically either in displacement or force control mode until the most overstressed rods reach a predetermined critical strain value. Then the broken rods are removed and the lattice configuration is recalculated to obtain a new equilibrium. This procedure is repeated until the network breaks fully apart. The force-displacement diagrams for simulated patterns are shown in Fig. 5. The aggregated pattern is weakest among the four while the regular distribution of fibres results in increased load-carrying capacity.

Figure 5. Loading diagrams for force (left) and displacement control (right).

The elliptic hard-core model is slightly stronger than the circular hard-core counterpart. This is because the nearest neighbour distances between fibres aligned close to the loading direction, i.e. at 90° to horizontal axis, are larger for the elliptic model resulting in a less severe stress interaction, Fig. 6.

Figure 6. Orientation distribution of nearest neighbour distances.

Figure 7. Percolating cracks for embedded cluster and regular patterns.

The fracture behaviour of aggregated and regular patterns are shown in Fig. 7. The patterns are embedded in the hard-core background in order to minimize an influence of the boundary con-

ditions. Two pre-existed microcracks are introduced at both sides of the patterns in order to initiate propagation of the percolating crack. The microcrack traces are identified with the length and the position of that side of the Dirichlet polygon which is perpendicular to the broken rod. The crack that percolates the window of observation avoids the path through the regular pattern indicating its resistance to fracture as compared to the clustered distribution of fibres. It is concluded that regularity in the fibres dispersion leads to increased load bearing capacity and resistance to crack propagation. Modelling of a microstructure by finite element method has customarily been based on a certain regularity assumption. However, microstructures do not have repeating patterns perhaps with the exception of crystals. In a light of the present study an analysis based upon the assumption of regularity of fibres distribution must necessarily lead to overestimation of strength and fracture properties as compared to real materials possessing disordered microstructure. Figure 8 illustrates transverse cracks in 90° plies of cross-ply laminates together with simulating results with the discrete model. The distribution pattern of the simulated model is exactly the same as for the glass fibre-epoxy composite. Simulated crack paths mirror transverse microcracks reasonably well.

Figure 8. Transverse cracks and their simulated counterparts.

The presented model introduces the disorder of a microstructure in a natural way and allows for an easy modification of breaking rules and disorder types which makes the analysis of fracture variability very flexible and straightforward.

REFERENCES

1. H.J. Herrmann and S. Roux (eds.), Statistical Models for the Fracture of Disordered Media, North-Holland, Amsterdam (1990).
2. J.C. Charmet, S. Roux and E. Guyon (eds.), Disorder and Fracture, Plenum Press, New York (1990).
3. M. Taya, K. Muramatsu, D.J. Lloyd and R. Watanabe, Determination of Distribution Patterns of Fillers in Composites by Micro-morphological Parameters, *JSME*, **34**, No. 2 (1991).
4. B. Altan, Z. Misirh and M. Yorucu, The Determination of the Homogeneity in Multiphase Mixtures, *Z. Metallkde*, **81**, 221-228 (1990).
5. R. Pyrz, Interpretation of Disorder and Fractal Dimensions in Transversely Loaded Unidirectional Composites, *Polym. & Polym. Comp.*, **1**, 283-295 (1993).
6. R. Pyrz, Quantitative Description of the Microstructure of Composites. Part I: Morphology of Unidirectional Composite Systems, *Comp. Sci. Techn.*, **50**, 197-208 (1994).
7. R. Pyrz, Correlation of Microstructure Variability and Local Stress Field in Two-Phase Materials, *Mat. Sci. Engng.*, **A177**, 253-259 (1994).
8. M.S. Axelsen and R. Pyrz, Correlation Between Fracture Toughness and Microstructure Morphology in Transversely Loaded Unidirectional Composites, in Proc. IUTAM Symposium on Microstructure-Property Interactions in Composite Materials, ed. R. Pyrz, Kluwer, Dordrecht 1995, 15-26.
9. M.S. Axelsen, Quantitative Description of the Morphology and Microdamages of Composite Materials, Ph.D. Thesis, Institute of Mechanical Engineering, Special Report No. 26, Aalborg University, 1995.
10. R. Pyrz and B. Bochenek, Statistical Model of Fracture in Materials with Disordered Microstructure, *Sci. Engng. Comp. Mat.*, **3**, 95-109 (1994).
11. R. Pyrz and B. Bochenek, Discrete Model of Fracture in Disordered Two-Phase Materials, in Proc. IUTAM Symposium on Microstructure-Property Interactions in Composite Materials, ed. R. Pyrz, Kluwer, Dordrecht 1995, 313-326.

